

Experiments on the influence of gravity on elementary particles needed

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Abstract

The influence of gravity on free electrons and their movements was investigated for the first time by Witteborn and Fairbanks in 1967, however several other authors including Schiff and Barnhill, but also Dessler, Michel, Rohrschach and Trammel described effects which can in generally compensate gravitational effects on electrons inside a copper drift tube as used by Witteborn and Fairbanks which are up to 10^5 to 10^6 times larger as the gravitational effects which are expected here. Therefore the question of how gravity works on elementary particles remains open up until now and needs to be investigated experimentally.

L'influence de la gravité sur les électrons libres et leurs mouvements a fait l'objet d'une étude par Witteborn et Fairbanks pour la première fois en 1967. Cependant, plusieurs autres auteurs, notamment Schiff et Barnhill, mais aussi Dessler, Michel, Rohrschach et Trammel ont décrit des effets pouvant généralement compenser les effets gravitationnels sur des électrons à l'intérieur d'un tube à dérive en cuivre, tel que celui utilisé par Witteborn et Fairbanks, qui sont jusqu'à 10^5 à 10^6 fois plus importants que les effets gravitationnels escomptés ici. Par conséquent, la question de savoir comment fonctionne la gravité sur les particules élémentaires demeure ouverte jusqu'à présent et doit faire l'objet d'études expérimentales.

Introduction

The influence of gravity on free electrons and their movements was investigated by Witteborn and Fairbanks in 1967 and 1968^{1,2}. These investigators used an electron cathode ray in a copper drift tube directed toward the sky, one meter from the ground, and measured t_{\max} , the maximum deceleration of the electrons. They saw no influence by the gravitational field and concluded that the effective acceleration, g_{eff} , and/or the effective gravitational mass, m_{eff} , of free electrons was zero or near zero^{1,2}.

On the other hand, many other researchers have shown that there are a number of other effects that must be considered when using this experimental setup.

Of these effects, the two most important are the so-called Schiff Barnhill Effect³ and the Dessler Michel Rohrschach Trammel (DMRT) Effect⁴. The DMRT Effect, in particular, can be used to compensate for much larger gravitational effects on electrons, as much as one million times what is theorized⁴.

From these theoretical considerations, gravity would be expected to have a much stronger than anticipated (10^5 to 10^6 times) influence on the movements of free electrons and ions if their rest masses were taken into account (rest mass is the gravitational mass).

This huge effect predicted by the DMRT Effect has not yet been seen experimentally; therefore, we are encouraging all experimentalists to investigate the influence of gravity on elementary particles and/or single ions. Useful experiments would examine the movements of free falling electrons and/or ions in the gravitational field. To explore falling-parabolas, researchers should focus only on electrons and/or ions with small velocities and the effective g-field and/or effective gravitational masses working on them. Drift tubes should not be used because the number of compensatory effects is great^{3,4}. We suggest condensation chambers or vacuum chambers as superior experimental settings.

To adequately consider gravity, the effective g-field and/or effective gravitational masses of the well-known basic elementary particles (proton, negatron, neutron, electron, and/or positron) must be experimentally determined. The question of how gravity works on elementary particles is as yet un-investigated and unsolved.

Experiment Proposal for a confirmation of the combined nature of gravity and electricity

According to the mass-charge binding theory, there should be an additional strong influence of the gravitational field on charged particles. This influence should thereby be stronger when compared to the influence of the gravitational field on the mass of elementary particles. Thereby this natural influence could not be shielded by any physical construction. Even if the electrostatic field can be shielded by appropriate physical constructions, the influence of the gravitational field on the charge would remain.

It could be expected that the interaction of charged particles with the gravitational field is stronger than the interaction of uncharged particles.

The CERN experiment Antihydrogen Experiment Gravity, Interferometry, Spectroscopy (AEgiS) seems to be most useful experiment currently been carried out to check this theory in a special way.

The primary scientific goal of the AEgiS Antihydrogen Experiment is the direct measurement of the Earth's gravitational acceleration on antihydrogen atoms. The AEgiS experiment is an international collaboration of physicists from all over Europe. In the first phase of the experiment, antiprotons from the Antiproton Decelerator are used, together with a pulse of laser-excited positronium atoms, to make a pulse of horizontally-travelling antihydrogen atoms.

These atoms then pass through an instrument called a Moiré deflectometer. A system of gratings in the deflectometer splits the antihydrogen beam into parallel rays, thus forming a periodic pattern. Once the antiatoms arrive at a certain point, they will annihilate upon contact with matter. Since areas behind the gratings are shadowed, while those behind the slits are not, the annihilation points reproduce the periodic pattern. The annihilation points are measured with a very precise detector combining silicon strips and photographic emulsion plates. From these patterns, conclusions are drawn on how much the antihydrogen atoms of different velocities drop during their horizontal flight, and thus determine the strength of the gravitational force between the Earth and the antihydrogen atoms. In this way the AEgiS experiment aims to carry out the first direct measurement of a gravitational effect on an antimatter system.

Taken together within the AEgiS experiment, CERN wants to make anti-hydrogen and then measure the acceleration of anti-H in the gravitational field of the earth. Similar experiments are performed with hydrogen and the question to be investigated is whether there is a difference in the interaction of gravitation with matter and/or with anti-matter.

Of course this experiment is intrinsically very interesting. However, it would be not less interesting (or even more interesting) to test the effect of the gravitational field of the earth on charged and un-charged particles as protons and/or anti-protons and on neutrons, as well as on electrons and/or positrons and on neutrinos. Using the same detectors as used in the original AEgIS experiment and using matter-antimatter annihilation radiation for detecting the particles, charged antimatter particles (anti-protons, anti-electrons) and uncharged antimatter particles (anti-neutrons, anti-hydrogen) would even be more suitable for performing the experiments proposed here than using matter particles. So we can just repeat the AEgIS experiments by using anti-electrons (positrons), anti-protons (negatrons) as well as by using anti-neutrons and anti-hydrogen (see the experimental set-up in figure 1). It is already clear that the heavier particles - protons and/or antiprotons and neutrons and/or anti-neutrons - would be considerably easier to measure since they have significantly greater mass.

There are two references from 1967 in which previous experiments on the interactions of gravity with charged particles were performed. However, in these experiments no influence or only a very slight influence of the gravitational field of the earth on electrons could be detected. By performing the AEgIS experiment with charged particles, a stronger effect of gravity on charged particles would be expected, according to the considerations made here, than on uncharged particles.

Further experiments would include simple falling experiments determine the time a particle needs to fall down towards the earth in a falling-tube. Again these falling experiments should be carried out with charged and with un-charged particles such as electrons, protons, neutrons and/or with hydrogen atoms. Again according to the considerations made here, the charged particles should always fall faster with a higher acceleration if compared to the uncharged particles. It should also be impossible to shield against this effect by any physical construction because this effect would be fixed by the nature of gravity and electricity and would not be a disturbing side effect.

Figure 1

experimental setup

References

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